

Challenges and aspirations: lived experiences of teacher-education student-mothers of a state university

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused significant disruptions in education globally leading to the implementation of different learning modalities. And it highly affects the most vulnerable groups such as women and children. This study explored the lived experiences of teacher-education student-mothers of a state university in the Philippines towards the end of the pandemic using a phenomenological approach. Twenty-one student-mothers voluntarily participated in the study who were i) bona fide students of the campus, ii) biological mothers, iii) married or living together with a partner, and iv) living with their child. From the data analyses, four major themes emerged: i) unexpected pregnancy, ii) heightened stress during the pandemic, iii) maintaining a positive outlook in life, and iv) managing dual roles. These results implied that the teacher-education student-mothers were highly stressed during the pandemic but they had extrinsic motivators to finish studies such as their children and family. The lived experiences of teacher-education student-mothers can serve as an inspiration to other students to pursue their studies even amid adversities. It is recommended that there must be an enhancement of student services tailored to support the mental health of marginalized students.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of the coronavirus disease in 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic hampered the educational system globally. It also affected the most vulnerable groups such as elders, women, and children in developing countries such as the Philippines. The majority of adolescent mothers struggle to balance their current responsibilities of being a student, a wife, and a mother at such a young age. Adolescent women manage academic, home, and child-rearing commitments amidst the pandemic.

College students' mental health has been significantly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. Throughout the epidemic, a large number of pupils saw a worsening in their mental health, with higher rates of anxiety and sadness. The shift to online learning, inactivity, and trouble adjusting to the new environment are some of the factors that have led to these mental health issues [1]. Furthermore, the epidemic has made pre-existing problems worse, like food shortages and financial hardships, which has further harmed students' academics and mental health.

Moreover, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on minorities such as college students' mental health is poorly studied in academic research. There have only been a few studies on the situation of student-

mothers in higher educational institutions [2]. Many studies about the pandemic also found that there was an increase in mental health issues among students which influenced their motivation, concentration, and social interactions [3] which are crucial factors for students to succeed in their education. Several reports of the pandemic's detrimental effects on mental health have been proven [4]. The pandemic can have long-term consequences for students [5]. Moreover, both teachers and students were under more stress because of the sudden changes in their lives as well as the uncertainty brought about by the pandemic.

Throughout the pandemic, student-mothers have experienced a range of difficulties and pressures. They have had to juggle a lot of obligations, such as supporting their kids' online study, being housewives, and continuing their education. These mothers find that online learning does not adequately meet their children's demands for intellectual and social development, therefore the transition from traditional classroom instruction to online learning has not been simple [6]. Subsequently, to lessen the psychological effects of the epidemic on student moms and their families, it is imperative to offer them support and focused mental health treatments.

As highlighted in the sustainable development goals (SDGs), education is fundamental to achieving the global objective of gender equality, which includes ensuring the safety of women and girls and putting an end to all forms of discrimination against them. Every person, regardless of sex, now can realize their full potential as a result of this achievement. Considering that gender equality entails providing men and women with equal opportunities in education, both in public and private spheres [7]. Women's levels of educational engagement and occupational status have seen significant changes over the past few decades, and this has been attributed to their crucial role and contribution to economic development and national advancement.

With the onset of the pandemic in 2019, the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) of the Philippines proclaimed the prevalence of adolescent pregnancies a national social emergency. This urged the former President of the Philippines Rodrigo Duterte to sign Executive Order 14 in response to the urgency of the increasing number of teenage pregnancies. Adolescent pregnancy is also expensive because those who have completed high school earn more than those who have not. Surprisingly, the number of adolescent pregnancies has been rising in the Philippines over the past several years, and these young moms are typically underprivileged, live in rural regions, and have low educational levels [8].

By the end of 2020 and in the years following, there may be a significant number of unintended pregnancies among adolescents, particularly exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Highlighting the challenges faced by adolescent girls, with a substantial proportion experiencing unintended pregnancies during the pandemic period [9]. This study predicted that the health crisis could lead to a second crisis, particularly among teenagers.

This could obstruct the advancement of women's education and empowerment [10], which are crucial for a sustainable road to national development given the rising number of young student-mothers. Although there have been many research studies on the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on education, there have only been a few studies on the situation of student-mothers in higher educational institutions [11]. Hence, the study was conducted to focus on marginalized groups like student-mothers.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

The current study uses a qualitative design to investigate the lived experiences of college students who are also students in teacher education during the pandemic. In an effort to comprehend the student mother's lived experiences and draw meaning from them, a phenomenological method was used [12]. Additionally, the research concentrated on the phenomena of juggling the obligations of being a mother and a college student [13].

2.2. Participants and selection criteria

Twenty-one teacher-education student-mothers of Samar State University (Paranas Campus) were identified using purposive sampling who voluntarily participated in the study. The participants are enrolled in Bachelor of Elementary (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) programs on the campus. They met the inclusion criteria which are i) bona fide students of the campus, ii) biological mothers, iii) married or living together with a partner, and iv) living with their child.

2.3. Research instrument

To gain deeper insights into the real-life experiences of student-mothers, we employed a comprehensive research approach. First, we conducted individual in-depth interviews which allowed us to explore the unique challenges, coping strategies, and personal experiences of student-mothers. Additionally, we organized a focus group discussion (FGD), during which student-mothers came together to share their perspectives and engage in meaningful dialogue. Moreover, the FGD was facilitated using a set of carefully

crafted FGD guide questions which aimed to capture a holistic understanding of the roles faced by student-mothers. These interactions were thoughtfully chosen by the participants themselves to accommodate their schedules and ensure their active participation.

2.4. Data gathering

The researchers utilized an unstructured interview guide as the primary data collection method as this is the most suited for the study [14]. This approach was carefully chosen due to its suitability for our research objectives. Additionally, this allowed the researchers to gather essential information from the teacher-education student-mothers as the participants of the study. Lastly, it facilitated follow-up questions, enabling participants to elaborate further on their lived experiences.

2.5. Data analysis

The data gathered was analyzed using Collaizzi's method. This method aided the researchers in finding, understanding, describing, and depicting the lived experiences of teacher education student-mothers as they experience them, and later on, reveal emergent themes and their interwoven relationships. Each interview's data was gathered, organized, and carefully examined by the researchers to produce textural and structural descriptions of the participants' experiences [15].

2.6. Ethical consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Samar State University-Institutional Human Research Ethics Committee (SSU-IHREC) before the commencement of this study. Before the interview, the researchers also obtained the participants' informed consent. All participants were informed verbally and in writing about the purpose of the study and their right to discontinue participation at any time without having to provide a reason. Anonymity and confidentiality were guaranteed by ethical research standards.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the data analyses of the study, four themes emerged from the responses of student-mothers (SM): i) unexpected pregnancy, ii) heightened stress during the pandemic, iii) maintained a positive outlook in life, and iv) managed dual roles. Moreover, some subthemes emerged during the analyses which are also presented as follows:

3.1. Unexpected pregnancy

Theme 1 underscores the unexpected challenges faced by teacher-education student-mothers amid the pandemic's peak, revealing their lack of preparedness for early parenthood while pursuing their studies. This theme also highlights their swift adjustment to embracing the responsibilities of motherhood, often without prior awareness of their pregnancy. Understanding these experiences is essential for educational institutions to provide adequate support systems tailored to the unique needs of student-mothers, nurturing an environment conducive to both academic success and maternal well-being.

Subtheme 1. Abortion was never a choice.

SM-03: *"Not prepared to have another child this pandemic but I want to keep it."*

SM-13: *"Actually I am not prepared to be pregnant; this is my destiny so I embraced it."*

SM-15: *"I have accepted my pregnancy and know my responsibilities as a mother."*

SM-18: *"I consider my pregnancy as a gift from God."*

SM-21: *"When I became pregnant, I trusted myself that I could become a good mother."*

Students engage in alcoholism as their coping strategy [16] and premarital sex between young people can occur and is becoming more accepted, and there is less pressure from society to legalize pregnancies that are not born with a woman's consent [8]. Moreover, the study by Once *et al.* [17] emphasized that there is still a high incidence rate of poverty which implies that there is something wrong in the system. One of the reasons for this is early pregnancy and lack of education both in urban and rural communities in Samar, Philippines as supported by the study of Mustacisa *et al* [18]. Motherhood is one of several obstacles faced by student-mothers as they work toward their degrees. In actuality, college students socialize with new people, form new friendships and organizations, attend parties, and occasionally engage in sexual activity that could result in an unplanned pregnancy [19] which implies that unwanted pregnancies are becoming prevalent due to societal norms globally.

3.2. Heightened stress during the pandemic

Theme 2 suggests that teacher-education student-mothers encountered significant stress levels throughout the pandemic. This stress stemmed from the demanding juggling act of being a student, a mother,

and often a wife simultaneously. The transition to online learning exacerbated their struggles, as it became increasingly challenging to effectively manage their time at home amidst other responsibilities. These findings underscore the immense burden placed on student-mothers during the pandemic, highlighting the urgent need for support systems and flexible educational approaches that accommodate their diverse roles and alleviate their stress.

Subtheme 1. Several responsibilities are stressful.

SM-06: *"Multitasking is really stressful for me as a mother and student at the same time."*

SM-07: *"Doing academic tasks at home while answering modules of my daughter and attending to the needs of my husband is hard."*

SM-13: *"I feel so stressed because I am struggling financially, emotionally, and mentally."*

SM-16: *"I have been neglecting my own health because of heavy responsibilities that are burdened on my shoulders. I encountered too much stress and anxiety."*

SM-18: *"I was restless and lonely during the pandemic; I was not even sure if I would still continue studying."*

Student-mothers can commit suicide as a result of maternity and mental health conditions [20] such as postpartum depression and anxiety. Additionally, time conflicts, the need to combine employment, school, and parenting, financial limitations, and other socioeconomic issues are ongoing obstacles for student-mothers to finish a post-secondary degree during the pandemic [21]. Hence, the pandemic added a burden to the lives of student-mothers. In addition, women have experienced increased stress during the COVID-19 pandemic. Studies have shown that factors such as depression, nervousness, and anxiety contribute to the overall stress levels faced by working women, including working students during the pandemic [22].

3.3. Maintained a positive outlook in life

Theme 3 suggests that teacher-education student-mothers maintained a resilient and positive outlook despite their challenges. They viewed struggles as integral to achieving success and finding motivation in their families and children. Despite the difficulties, these student-mothers made a conscious decision to persevere and continue their studies, demonstrating their dedication to personal and academic growth. This theme highlights the importance of resilience and determination in overcoming obstacles, serving as an inspiration to others facing similar circumstances.

Subtheme 1. Highly motivated to become successful.

SM-02: *"I am motivated and inspired in my studies so that I'll become a professional teacher someday."*

SM-03: *"I am proud to say that I will graduate and finish my studies even though I am a mother and I have children."*

SM-08: *"Parenting experience gives me the inspiration to continue my educational pursuits to become a model to my children."*

SM-10: *"I can finish my studies even if I am a mother and I will become a professional someday."*

SM-11: *"I am brave enough to reach my goals and be patient in every situation you encounter."*

While teacher-education student-mothers were dealing with the difficulties of adolescent pregnancy and college education during the pandemic, they recognized the value of education, found the strength to persevere for their children, and dreamed of a better future for their families [23]. Additionally, female students are more likely to work on homework for extended periods in class and are less likely to get bored or discouraged. All of which can help them succeed academically. Physical exercise and spiritual coping strategies were also adopted by some of them to keep a good attitude in life [24]. Furthermore, in the face of stress, that is, internal and/or external pressures that are perceived to exceed one's available resources, individuals cope one way or another [25]. Implying that the student-mothers looked at the silver lining of their experiences.

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has had varying effects on the life satisfaction of women. Female academicians who had to work and learn from home during the pandemic reported a moderate level of life satisfaction, with increased time spent on academic development and personal activities positively impacting their contentment with life [26]. Parents, especially mothers, experienced sharper declines in life satisfaction during the first lockdown, and further pandemic stressors led to even lower satisfaction during subsequent lockdowns [27]. Factors such as being a woman, living in urban areas, having fewer social interactions, and concerns about infection and death were found to increase the likelihood of life dissatisfaction among adults in South Korean communities [27]. Surprisingly in Southeast Asia, some families experienced worsened relationships during the early days of the crisis [28], [29].

3.4. Managed dual roles

Theme 4 suggests that teacher-education student-mothers adeptly handle dual roles with determination and efficacy. They prioritize completing their studies despite their maternal responsibilities,

demonstrating that motherhood does not impede their educational pursuits. These student-mothers skillfully fulfill both their roles as students and mothers, showcasing their ability to balance academic and familial obligations. This theme underscores the resilience and capability of student-mothers to manage multiple roles and responsibilities simultaneously.

Subtheme 1. Student-mothers are good at multitasking.

SM-01: *"I need to comply with all my academic requirements for me to graduate whatever it takes."*

SM-04: *"I want to finish my studies and be successful in this chosen career to provide the needs and wants of my children."*

SM-07: *"I manage my time because I want to finish my course to pass the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) and to have permanent work that has a sufficient income."*

SM-11: *"The pandemic will not stop me from finishing my degree, passing the board, getting a lifetime career, and being a role model for my kids."*

SM-14: *"I want to finish my studies and have a good job so that I can lift my family out of poverty."*

The disparities in academic performance between male and female students are caused by a variety of factors [21]. This contains the things that encourage mothers who are also students to succeed in their studies. These student-mothers encountered both good and negative parenting during the pandemic, in addition to parental stress when engaging in home learning activities [14]. According to societal conventions, women solely perform domestic duties to benefit their husbands and families. Therefore, getting a degree would provide them with more authority because women earn more money when they have more education [21]. Furthermore, female students can do better in school because they have higher role models and sincerity in their studies [6] as they perform better in school compared to boys [30]. This implies that student-mothers are good at multitasking.

Moreover, during the pandemic, women and mothers have taken on dual roles and faced various challenges, both positive and negative. They have had to balance their work responsibilities with increased household and caregiving duties [31], [32]. Student-mothers faced significant challenges during the pandemic, balancing their roles as parents and students. They experienced heightened stress due to the increased responsibilities of caregiving, homeschooling, and academic pursuits [33]. Working-student-mothers have experienced role blurring and barriers in managing their roles as mothers, workers, and students due to remote work, school closures, and remote learning [34]. On a positive note, they have shown resilience by relying on spirituality, self-efficacy, and self-assessment to cope with economic, family, educational, and cultural problems [35].

4. CONCLUSION

From the findings, the study concluded that university student-mothers encountered difficulties in managing both their academic and motherhood responsibilities. The study highlights heightened stress levels among student-mothers during the pandemic, yet they exhibited resilience and determination to complete their studies, primarily fueled by extrinsic motivation derived from their familial responsibilities. Notably, despite facing challenges such as the health crisis, personal adversities, and academic hurdles, these student-mothers maintained a positive perspective on life.

The lived experiences of these individuals can serve as a source of inspiration for other student-mothers navigating similar challenges. Furthermore, it is suggested that a more comprehensive examination be undertaken to explore the longitudinal effects of the pandemic on the mental well-being of student-mothers. Such research can contribute to the enhancement of student services tailored to support the mental health needs of this demographic, ultimately fostering a more resilient academic community.

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